

INTERNAL CONTROL AND FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF LISTED DEPOSIT MONEY BANKS IN NIGERIA: AN ANALYTICAL REVIEW

IBEREDEM SENAM UKUT

Department of Accounting, University of Uyo, Nigeria.

iberedemsenam@gmail.com

+2348037945592

&

JOHN DOMINIC EKPOESE

Department of Accounting, University of Uyo, Nigeria.

ekpoese09@yahoo.com

+2347036471244

Abstract

This study aimed at investigating internal control and financial performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. This was motivated by the desire to learn how internal control enhances effective financial performance in the wake of the widespread corporate failures in Nigeria and the rest of the world. Control Environment, Risk Assessment, Control Activities, Information and Communication vis-a-vis Monitoring were represented by internal control while Return on Assets was used to represent financial performance. The study used census sampling technique to extract data from the annual reports of 13 deposit money banks listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group as of December 31st, 2018. Secondary data were gathered for the study. The study's seven-year time frame was from 2012 to 2018. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to examine the data specifically through regression analysis. The outcome of the data analysis showed that Control Environment, Risk Assessment, Control Activities, and Information and Communication significantly influence the financial performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. This implies that, Control Environment, Risk Assessment, Control Activities and Information and Communication put in place by banks influences at most 22.3%, -35.4%, 94.7% and 19.7% of the profit generated by the banks but monitoring insignificantly influence the financial performance of banks by 15.2% in Nigeria. As a result, it is advised, that Management of deposit money banks should maintain sound control environmental approach to internal control due to the riskiness of banking business and its impact on the economic growth of the country. Management should ensure that banks have an independent board of directors and audit committee as a corporate governance regulatory requirement in order to keep assessing the riskiness of their businesses.

Keywords: Internal Control, Financial Performance, Deposit money banks.

1. INTRODUCTION

Over the years, there have been significant bank failures and crises across the globe, with internal control weaknesses among the causes of these failures. The performance and sustainability of Nigerian banks have also been affected by financial mismanagement or misconduct by individuals in charge of corporate governance, which is seen as one of the main issues they face. Many scandals, including those involving the defunct Oceanic Bank International plc, Intercontinental Bank, and Bank PHB, all in Nigeria, the Alpha Bank in South Africa, and the Royal Bank of Zimbabwe, have been documented throughout history. According to reports, these banks used unethical accounting techniques to manipulate the accounting system and controls (Cohen, Holder -Webb, Nath and Wood, 2012). A national crisis could result from the failure of one financial institution if investors lose faith in the economy and jobs are lost.

Every organization must have internal control because it serves as the foundation for checks and balances (Kumuthinidevi, 2016). Internal control is, at its core, a procedure put in place by management to guarantee an organization's operational effectiveness and efficiency, the accuracy of its financial reporting, and its adherence to laws, rules, and policies. Everything that limits hazards to an organization is included in the broad definition of internal control. Internal control is a set of accounting and administrative policies and practices that guarantee the adherence to established policies, standards, and legal obligations as well as the protection of the company's assets. It is a method for managing and directing an organization's resources. It is crucial for detecting and stopping fraud as well as safeguarding the organization's tangible such as property, plant, and equipment and intangible resources reputation or intellectual property such as brand names and trademarks. As a result, an internal control system can be broken down into five different categories: control environment, risk assessment, control activities, information and communication as well as monitoring. An efficient internal control system typically makes it possible to achieve the goal of maximizing wealth (Ayagre, Gyamerah, and Nartey, 2014).

The various banks' financial results are used to gauge the banking industry's viability. The effectiveness of using the company's assets as well as returns on the wealth of the shareholders serve as metrics for measuring financial performance. Profitability is a key metric of financial performance. Return on assets, return on equity, and net interest margin are three often used metrics to determine how profitable a bank is. In this study, return on asset will be employed as a stand-in for financial performance. Scholars disagree on the relationship between internal control and financial performance. While some claimed that insufficient internal controls are to blame for bank failures, others claim that market pressures and other management factors, rather than weak internal controls, are to be blamed. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to determine how internal control systems affect deposit money banks' financial performance.

Fourteen out of the eighty-nine banks disappeared as a result of the 2004 banking sector reforms. In order to achieve the new capital requirement of 25 billion naira during these 18 months of the banking sector reform, there were a number of mergers and acquisitions among Nigerian banks. In the end, the 85 banks that existed in 2004 were reduced to 25 banks that were bigger and more financed. Another wave of bank failures occurred in Nigeria in 2009. These errors followed a joint CBN/NDIC special inquiry into the financial records of the 25 banks that were active in the nation in 2009. The investigation's key conclusions included that some banks were technically insolvent due to a lack of capital, inadequate credit risk management, inadequate liquidity, and a lack of corporate governance, which was attributed to a weak internal control system in banks, amidst other issues (Sanusi, 2009).

Internal control conversations are frequently conducted holistically without taking particular components into account. Due to this, evaluating internal control in relation to the financial performance of enterprises, particularly banks, has become extremely difficult. The internal control literature has a hole caused by this place. The limited studies on internal control systems that have been done concentrated on multiple investigations using questionnaire and survey research methods. This study's goal is to investigate the relationship between internal control and the financial performance of Nigeria's deposit money banks. The study's assumptions are broken down into the following hypotheses for analytical details.

- Ho₁:** There is no significant influence of control environment on return on assets of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria.
- Ho₂:** There is no significant influence of risk assessment on return on assets of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria.
- Ho₃:** There is no significant influence of control activities on the return on assets of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria.
- Ho₄:** There is no significant influence of information and communication on return on assets of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria.
- Ho₅:** There is no significant influence of monitoring on return on assets of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria.

The focus of this study was on the deposit money banks sector. While financial performance was measured by return on assets for the financial years 2012 through 2018. Internal control was divided into sections such as control environment, risk assessment, control activities, information and communication as well as monitoring for the indicated independent variables for the pertinent years.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK AND LITERATURE REVIEW

In the context of Nigeria's Deposit Money Banking industry, agency theory offers a tenable explanation for the connection between internal control and financial performance. Early in the 1970s, Stephen A. Ross and Barry M. Mitnick separately developed this notion. In the proceedings of the American Economic Review, which were published in May 1973, Stephen A. Ross established the economic theory of

agency. The institutional theory of agency developed by Barry M. Mitnick was presented at the annual meeting of the American Science Association in 1973 and was later made available on microfilm. Barry M. Mitnick presented the common logic of agency in institutional settings, despite the fact that Stephen A. Ross and Barry M. Mitnick's fundamental ideas are comparable. The principal's recommended behaviour never materializes since it is not worthwhile to make anything flawless. However, society has developed mechanisms that take care of these flaws, buffering them or adapting to be more chronically distorted by them. This broad method can be used to explain a variety of social behaviours, along with related arguments.

According to agency theory, a party (the principal) hires a different party (the agent) to carry out specific tasks on their behalf while also giving the agent some decision-making authority. Employer and employee relationships are arguably the most well-known examples of agency relationships. Others include the CEO, the shareholders, the elected representative from the constituency, the state's ambassador, and the agent. The local government electorate, or the general public, is emphasized as the principal in this study, while the local government chairmen are emphasized as the agent. By offering the basic residents the public goods and services they require, the Chairmen are expected to demonstrate excellent management of the resources entrusted to them.

The conundrum that the principal and agent, while typically striving toward the same goal, may not typically share the same interest, is one of the problems that result from this theory. As a result, the literature on this topic mostly focuses on the systems and methods that are used to try to align the interests of the principle and agent, as well as the repercussions that result from those actions. A separate theory of agency has not emerged since 1970s except that put forward by Stephen A. Ross and Barry M. Mitnick which independently presented this idea. Adams Smith had thought about the principal and agent dilemma in a corporate context as early as the 18th century, and many of its key concepts were developed in the literature. This study therefore, is anchoring on this theory.

An internal control system is described as "the whole system of controls, financial and otherwise established by management to carry on the business of the enterprise in an orderly and efficient manner, ensure adherence to management policies, safeguard the assets and secure, to the extent possible, the completeness and accuracy of the records" in the auditing standards. It is described as a methodical step taken by an organization to conduct business in an orderly and efficient manner, safeguard its resources, deter and detect errors, fraud, and theft, ensure the accuracy and completeness of its accounting data, generate trustworthy and timely financial and management information, and ensure adherence to its policies and plans.

Internal control, as defined by Millichamp (2002), is the entire system of controls, financial or otherwise, put in place by management in order to conduct an enterprise's business in an organized and effective manner, ensure adherence to management

policies, protect the assets, and, to the greatest extent possible, secure the completeness and accuracy of the records. Internal control, as defined by Gamage, Lock, and Fernando (2014), is the procedure that management, those responsible for governance, and other staff members design and implement to reasonably ensure that an entity's goals are met with regard to the accuracy and dependability of financial reporting, the effectiveness and efficiency of operations, and compliance with applicable laws and regulations. The organization's objectives are threatened by identified business risks, which is why the internal control system was developed and put into place.

According to Abiola (2013), the idea of internal control (IC) is crucial for the effective management of an organization's risk, which if disregarded could create obstacles to the achievement of its stated goals. Poor controls result in scandals, losses, failures, and reputational harm to a firm. When new enterprises are launched without a method of risk control, issues are likely to arise. The management's utilization of established rules and procedures to operate the company effectively is represented by the internal control system. Internal controls and internal procedures are part of the control system.

Internal control is defined as "Comprising the plan of an organization and all coordinated methods and measures adopted within a business to safeguard its assets, verify the accuracy and reliability of its accounting data, prorate operational efficiency, and ensure adherence to specified managerial policies." Financial internal control and non-financial internal control are the two categories within the definition of internal control. Financial internal control relates to financial activities and can be demonstrated through controls over the company's financing operations, management of receipts and payments, and cash receipts and payments controls. On the other hand, non-financial internal control deals with activities that are indirectly financial in nature, such as controls over the company's operations and personnel department, controls over non - current assets, and even controls over established procedures (Reid and Ashelby, 2002).

A strong internal control system aids a company in minimizing waste, fraud, and errors. Strengthened assets custody, assurance for management on the reliability of accounting data, removal of unfounded suspicion, and assistance in maintaining adequate and trustworthy accounting records (Amudo and Inanga, 2009). According to Treba (2003), internal control is a mechanism for ensuring that a company achieves its mission and goals. He adds that although accountants and auditors are frequently assumed to be in charge of internal controls, management actually has the major responsibility for effective controls.

Regularly evaluating the effectiveness of internal controls to ascertain if they are correctly designed and operating is a crucial component of any comprehensive internal control system (Treba, 2003). Internal controls can be divided into

administrative controls and accounting controls, according to ICAN (2014), these two are further classified into the following types;

- i. *Organization Control* which entails that every business should, in theory, have a plan for its organizational structure that specifies roles, assigns duties, and identifies reporting channels for every facet of the business' operations.
- ii. *Segregation of duties Control* stated how crucial to keep those responsibilities or tasks apart if they need to be integrated in order for one person to record and process an entire transaction. As a result, the aspect of checking is increased while the risks of purposeful manipulation or errors are decreased. Authorization, execution, custody, and recording, as well as system development and daily operations in the case of computer-based accounting systems, are among the functions that should be separated, particularly in banks.
- iii. *Physical control* mostly deals with the custody of assets and involve protocols and security precautions used to guarantee that only authorized individuals have access to assets. This covers both direct and indirect access through written materials. When dealing with cash or valuable, transportable, tradeable, or attractive items, these controls become crucial.
- iv. *Authorization and approval* indicate that every transaction needs to be authorized or approved by a responsible person. It is important to specify the parameters for those authorizations.
- v. *Arithmetic and approval* involve the recording function controls striving for all transactions that need to be recorded and processed being authorized, and are included appropriately and accurately. These checks include maintaining and looking for papers, as well as verifying the records' mathematical accuracy.
- vi. *Personnel* involves that procedures should exist to guarantee that employees are capable of handling their duties. Any control system should be put up with consideration for the qualifications, selection, and training of the employees involved as well as their individual personalities.
- vii. *Supervision* stresses that any system of internal control should include the supervision by responsible officials of day-to-day transactions and the recording thereof.
- viii. *Management* is concern with management implemented controls that are used outside of the system's normal operations. It covers the overall supervisory control that management exercises over the internal audit function, the assessment of management accounts and their comparison to budgets, and any other specific reviews. The aforementioned internal control categories were taken directly from the authorized auditing standards.

The following five elements make up an "effective" internal control system and aid in achieving a company's mission, strategies, and related business goals. The internal control components are made up of the five segment as listed in ISA 315.

- a) *Control Environment* constitutes the general attitude of management and staff in the organization toward internal control and is frequently referred to as the

control environment. The management's opinions, awareness of internal control, and actions are all part of the control environment. It also establishes the foundation of an organization and covers management duties and governance. It serves as the framework for effective internal management by offering direction and structure. The following components make up the control environment; authority and responsibility delegation, participation of management, management's operating philosophy, communication and enforcement of integrity and ethical values, commitment to competence, organizational structure, and human resource policies and practices. A control environment is frequently referred to as a "internal control environment" and is a concept in enterprise risk management, internal audit, and financial audit. It refers to how directors and management, or "those charged with governance," generally feel about the internal control system and how crucial it is for the company. They do so through managerial style, business culture, values, operational style, organizational structure, and policies and procedures pertaining to human resources. Management often exhibits a high level of commitment to setting up and maintaining suitable controls in a strong control environment. Although the presence of a robust control environment cannot ensure that controls are running successfully, it is considered a positive aspect in the risk assessment process by the auditor. The overall effectiveness of the control system is likely to be low without a robust control environment.

b) Risk assessment is the next significant internal control component. The potential occurrences that endanger the accomplishment of goals are known as risks. However, it has an impact on an organization's capacity to carry out its objective. The process of finding, evaluating, and choosing how to handle these items is known as risk assessment. At every level of an organization, there are risks that could inhibit the accomplishment of set objectives. These risks can be internal or external. Management should therefore take the required steps to reduce these risks.

c) Control activities are instruments, both manual and automated, that aid in preventing or reducing hazards that may obstruct the achievement of the organization's goals and mission. To execute the organization's goals and mission effectively and efficiently, management needs to set up control activities. The policies and processes that help ensure that the required steps are done to handle the risks associated in achieving the entity's objectives are known as control activities, according to Messier (1997). Performance reviews, information processing, general IT controls, application controls, physical controls, and segregation of roles are the different categories of internal controls listed in ISA 315. The rules and processes that help guarantee that the required steps are taken to address risks to the attainment of the entity's objectives, whether they are within IT or manual systems, are known as control activities. "The directors are responsible for the preparation of financial statements that give a true and fair view in accordance with the Financial Reporting Standards issued by the Institute of Certified Public Accountants and for such internal control as the directors determine is necessary" forming an opinion and reporting on financial statements. The relationship between internal controls and the

remainder of the audit should be understood by auditors. Additionally, they must learn how to recognize control actions at the business process level.

d) *Information and communication* focus on the types and standards of information required for efficient control, as well as the reports used to provide that information. To help management achieve organizational goals, information is required at all organizational levels. Both insiders and outsiders make advantage of the knowledge. From top to bottom, this information should be distributed in a way and at a pace that enables the recipients to carry out their duties. Infrastructure such as physical and hardware components, software, people, processes, and data all make up an information system. Infrastructure and software will be absent, or have less significance, in systems that are exclusively or primarily manual, as opposed to computerized. Since most modern systems, including those in small organizations, heavily rely on information technology (IT), the majority of examination questions will probably be based in some way on computerized systems. Recognizing this is crucial, and you must make sure that any audit tests or controls you recommend for such a system are acceptable. For instance, there is no purpose in recommending that staff members be seen filling out order forms if orders are submitted online. The best course of action would be to place a "test" order on the website and check if it has been logged by viewing the order on screen. According to ISA 315, the auditor must comprehend the management's usage of the business information systems, including the accounting systems, to the degree that these systems may have an impact on the financial reporting process. The principal business transactions of the entity, how they and other events relevant to the financial reporting process are captured, identified and recorded by the entity, the processing methods, both manual and computerized, applied to those transactions, the accounting records, both manual and computerized, used to support the figures appearing in the financial statements, and more are all part of this aspect of the auditor's work.

e) *Monitoring* takes into account the fact that internal control procedures and their implementation alter over time. This may be brought on by the hiring of new employees, inconsistent application of processes or supervision, a lack of time or resources, or modifications to the conditions for which the internal control system was first intended. Therefore, management must assess and monitor whether the internal control system is still applicable to and functioning as intended in the entity. Monitoring is done to check on the effectiveness, efficiency, and proper execution of internal controls. The final element of internal control, monitoring, is a procedure that evaluates the effectiveness of internal control over time. Monitoring is the review of an organization's actions and transactions to determine the effectiveness of controls and the level of performance over time. To achieve the goals of the organization, management should prioritize monitoring internal control. Monitoring might be carried either by continuing tasks or independent assessments. Ongoing management and supervision tasks like assessing the reasonableness of management reports or continuously monitoring customer complaints are examples of regular management and supervision tasks. Separate evaluations are monitoring operations carried out on an irregular basis, such as recurring internal auditor audits.

The principles of internal controls as outlined by the Committee of Sponsoring Organizations of the Treadway Commission (COSO) and the U.S. Government Accountability Office (GAO) federal internal control standards are incorporated successfully into enterprise risk management (ERM). The underlying assumption is that management needs access to reliable information to keep its internal control system functioning and accomplish organizational goals. But occasionally, management is powerless to stop the risk from happening. Management should decide in these circumstances whether to accept the risk, decrease it to acceptable levels, or avoid it altogether. In order to accomplish its intended goal, management should ensure that each risk is appropriately assessed and handled. Management should continuously detect, assess, and manage company risks within a robust internal control framework. Events or omissions that could prohibit the entity from attaining its goals are considered significant business risks. Recognizing hazards or prospective risks is the same as identifying them.

In order to assess the risks, one must first determine whether they are considerable and, if necessary, rank them in terms of importance. Creating and putting into place controls and other risk-reduction strategies is known as risk management. According to ISA 315, the auditor is required to comprehend the management's risk assessment procedures utilized by the client firm to the extent that those procedures may have an impact on the financial reporting process. The operating environment in which the entity operates, new employees, new or improved information systems, rapid growth, new technology, new business models, products, or activities, corporate restructurings, expanded foreign operations, and new accounting pronouncements are just a few examples of the circumstances that can cause risks to emerge or change.

Researchers have been very concerned about measuring internal control components. In several studies, questionnaires are used to measure internal control components (Sawalga and Qtish (2012), Uwaoma and Ordu (2015), Chunlan, Huoyan, and Quan (2010) created a quantitative and comprehensive internal control evaluation methodology. The validity and reliability of questionnaires have been heavily challenged, thus this study adopted and modified Chunlan, *et al.* (2010) model. The model is explained as follows;

The five components of the internal control evaluation index system, internal control environment, risk assessment, control activities, information and communication, and monitoring can be created thoroughly and systemically. According to Chunlan *et al.* (2010), the basic design of an internal control system consists of the five core components, followed by a more intricate system that creates 28 secondary level indexes. Chunlan *et al.* (2010), added that, the primary components and secondary indices are defined as follows;

i) *Control environment* is often implemented by businesses on the basis of their management structures, institutional arrangements, responsibility allocation, internal audit, human resources policy, and corporate culture. These components serve as the foundation for all other elements of internal control and reflect the attitudes and understanding of corporate management, the board of directors, and

business owners toward internal control in the workplace. Values, inducement and incentive mechanisms, spiritual direction, staff capacity, management philosophy and working style, organizational structure, rules and regulations, and personnel policies are only a few examples of control environment components. The main concern with evaluation is that management must fully explain the integrity of internal control and must instill awareness and consciousness of control among all employees, especially senior management, who must actively exercise control. At the same time, staff members' abilities and responsibilities must align. Chunlan, *et al.* (2010) established seven secondary level indexes from the aforementioned definition, including management quality, integrity, and values; management philosophy and operating style; board of directors and audit committee; organizational structure; culture; and allocation of rights and responsibilities. The number of board committees was chosen as one of the seven indexes to be employed in this study's evaluation. The decision to use the number of board committees as a proxy for the control environment was driven by the fact that the various committees oversee and advise on the implementation of controls in the banks. This sets the work apart from other research like that of Chunlan *et al.* (2010), which evaluated the control environment using the seven indices *et al.* simultaneously by numbering each one using 0 and 1.

ii) *Risk assessment* relates to how the firm promptly recognizes and systematically assesses the risks connected with implementing internal control objectives in day-to-day business operations, then decides on reasonable risk mitigation strategies. The focus on overall goals, the development and convergence of operational activity objectives, risk identification and assessment, risk analysis including risk likelihood and risk impact on the company objectives, and risk response mechanism are some of the parts of risk assessment. Chunlan *et al.* (2010) established nine secondary-level indexes based on the aforementioned definition, including adaptability of goal-setting, scientific rigor in the development of objectives, level of goal-setting, suitability of the use of risk identification techniques, suitability of risk assessment techniques, risk likelihood, risk impact on business goals and risk response mechanism. Because it is their duty to assess risk and advise the bank on necessary adjustments to the risk management plan, the number of risk management committee members was utilized as a stand-in for risk assessment for the purposes of this study. This distinguishes the research from other studies like Chunlan *et al.* (2010), who evaluated the risk assessment using all nine indicators simultaneously and assigned numbers to them using the numbers 0 and 1.

iii) *Control activity* stated that, to keep risks within the acceptable range using appropriate control measures based on the findings of risk assessment, it is necessary to provide adequate assurance of the enterprise's management goals. The overall effectiveness of the control system, which reflects every aspect of operations including finance, investment, money, payment, purchase, production, sales, contracts, security, and distribution as well as ensuring the accuracy and value of accounting report information, should be one of the components of control activity.

The index on whether there is a workable performance assessment system, the index on its practical application, and the index on whether the control system of properties change for sending and receiving is perfect or effective Chunlan, *et al.* (2010) established four secondary-level indexes integrated; accounting process control, operating process control, property security control, and performance evaluation. This was done because control activity relates to every aspect and corner of the production, operation, and management of the enterprise and the evaluation cannot cover everything. Because all four indices are always on the agenda at board meetings, the number of board meetings was chosen as a stand-in for control actions for the purposes of this study. Therefore, the likelihood that the control operations in the bank will be effective increases with the frequency of board meetings.

iv) *Information and Communication* has to do with the organization's timely and accurate collection and transfer of internal control related information, allowing for effective internal and external communication of the information. The gathering and collation of internal and external information must be taken into consideration while analyzing internal control information. At the same time, we must pay attention to the communication's routes and techniques for exchanging internal and external information. The comprehensiveness, security, and patency of information should also be taken into consideration, particularly in the current highly developed information technology world. Four secondary-level indexes information system, information quality, communication routes, and communication ways were established by Chunlan *et al.*, (2010). As a stand-in for information and communication in this case, the natural log of the bank's investment in information systems such as computer hardware was used. This was inspired by the idea that the bank's information system will be stronger, when more money is invested in it.

v) *Monitoring* constitutes a general word for the administration and oversight of internal control by the business management department as well as the re-monitoring and re-evaluation activities of internal control by the internal audit and monitor departments. The business monitors and examines the situation surrounding the creation and application of internal controls, assesses their efficacy, identifies their shortcomings, and promptly improves the procedure. Internal control supervisory reviews can be conducted continually, infrequently, separately, or jointly. The rationale of the report on internal control inadequacies and the modification of the policy process should be the primary concerns of the supervisory review procedure. The four secondary level indexes that was set up as a result are continuous monitoring, separate evaluation, report deficiency, and deficiency rectification methods. Although the internal audit function is primarily responsible for monitoring, the type of external auditor that auditing the bank was employed as a stand-in for monitoring in this study because the goal was to evaluate internal control using quantitative data. The decision to use these proxies were made in light of the fact that the external auditor also keeps an eye on and reports on internal control deficiencies.

Vu (2016) conducted research on the elements influencing the performance of internal control systems in Vietnamese commercial banks. His primary goal was to ascertain how internal control system components affected commercial banks' performance. Multiple regression analysis (MRA) was employed by the researcher for the analysis. Political institutions and interest groups were discovered by the researcher to be two additional aspects that affect the efficacy of internal control systems in Vietnamese commercial banks.

A study on effective internal control systems as a remedy for trouble in the Nigerian banking sector was conducted by Tunji (2013). The study's major goal was to determine how effective internal control systems contributed to the reduction or eradication of distresses in Nigeria's banking industry. 56 employees of particular deposit money banks were employed in a survey research design, and data were gathered utilizing questionnaires. While the demographic data of the respondents was analyzed using simple percentages, four research hypotheses were posed and tested. The hypotheses were examined using the t-test statistic at a significant level of 5%. The results of the testing of the hypotheses showed that; the existence of an efficient internal control system has a positive impact on the elimination of fraud in banks; the efficiency of the internal control system can be accurately determined; the efficiency of the internal control system has a significant impact on the accuracy and reliability of bank records; and bank distresses were linked to non-compliance with the internal control system's established procedures. According to the findings, it was advised that banks hire qualified accountants to handle their internal control tasks because only an internal control system that is both functional and effective can be used to thoroughly check for and prevent mismanagements, which typically cause financial distress in the banking sector.

Ayagre, Gyamerah and Nartey (2014) evaluated the control environment and monitoring activities components of Internal Control Systems of Ghanaian Banks using COSO's principles and attributes of assessing the effectiveness of internal control systems. They sought to establish a link between internal control elements and bank performance in Ghana. The effectiveness of the bank's internal control system was assessed together with respondents' knowledge and perceptions of internal controls using a five-point Likert scale. Responses ranged from strongly disagree (SD) to strongly agree (SA), with 1 denoting strongly disagree and 5 denoting either strongly agree. Data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) and reported as means and standard deviations for each question and segment of the questionnaire. The study discovered that the monitoring activities and control environment components of the internal control systems of Ghanaian banks have robust controls. Respondents gave the two components high marks, with average values of 4.72 and 4.66, respectively. The report made the recommendation that the boards of Ghanaian banks should not get complacent in light of the results but instead work hard to maintain continual ongoing and independent internal control monitoring to ensure that controls are actually in place and are operating as intended.

Kumuthiridevi (2016) studied the Effectiveness of Internal Control System in the Private Banks of Trincomalee. The researcher found through observation and discussion that there are some deviations in the internal control system in the daily banking activities. The researcher aimed to accomplish the following goals based on this issue and evaluate the bank's control environment and internal control system; identify the bank's risk assessment process and internal control; evaluate the bank's accounting, information, and communication system relevant to financial reporting and internal control; determine how the bank's control activities affect internal control in the bank. Effective internal control served as the dependent variable for this study, which also took into account five independent variables: the control environment, risk assessment, accounting, information and communication, control activities, and self-evaluation. Data were gathered for this study from both primary and secondary sources to assess the association between two variables. Questionnaires are the primary source of primary data. The regular personnel of eleven banks received the questionnaires. Additionally, both univariate and bivariate analysis techniques were applied to the data analysis and evaluation. Mean, standard deviation, and percentages were employed in the univariate analysis to evaluate the data. All independent variables are only mildly supportive of the effectiveness of the internal control system, according to the data evaluation. And when all independent factors were taken into account collectively, they were somewhat supportive of the efficiency of the internal control system. The researcher also provided a summary of the data analysis under the conclusion and recommendations section and suggested certain changes to be made to the bank's internal control system.

Sawalga and Qtish (2012) examined the relationship between some components such as risk assessment, control environment and control activities of internal control system and the effectiveness of audit program in Jordan. The goal of their research was to determine how internal control elements and Jordan's audit program's efficacy interacted. The study's findings, which are based on 43 valid questionnaires demonstrated that a risk assessment does considerably contribute to a successful audit program. However, the analysis's findings show that the control environment and control activities do not significantly support a successful audit program. These findings suggest that Jordanian businesses lack the expertise needed to work with the present internal control evaluation tools. For both company management and outside auditors, some applications and suggestions were made.

3. METHODOLOGY

An *ex-post facto* research design was used in the study. This method makes use of data that has already been collected to assess the statistical correlation between and among the study's variables. The research population includes the 13 companies in the deposit money banks category that were listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group as of December 31, 2018. 13 banks were taken into account as the study's population utilizing the census sampling technique based on the accessibility and availability of their annual reports for the study's duration. In the study, 91 sample points were taken into account. Secondary data for the study was derived from publicly accessible

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

4.1 Empirical Analysis

The data analysis for the study was done using Statistical Package for Social Science version 20 at 5% level of significance. The analysis includes descriptive and regression analyses.

Table 4.1: Descriptive Statistics of the variables

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std.	Skewness	Kurtosis		
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Deviation	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic
						Std. Error		Std. Error	
Control Environment	91	4.00	8.00	5.5055	0.94720	.425	.253	-.182	.500
Risk Assessment	91	3.00	12.00	6.9560	1.74427	.197	.253	.345	.500
Control Activities	91	2.00	13.00	5.9670	1.94622	1.101	.253	1.726	.500
Information And Communication (N'000)	91	135552.00	9915000.00	3162580.62	2453912.04	.892	.253	-.019	.500
Monitoring	91	0.00	1.00	.7692	.42366	-1.300	.253	-.319	.500
Financial Performance (%)	91	-9.53	22.65	2.3778	4.02799	2.170	.253	9.669	.500
Valid N (Listwise)	91								

Source: *Researcher's Analytic Output (2023)*

Table 4.1 provides the descriptive statistics of the study's data set. The minimum, maximum, mean, and standard deviation are its constituent parts. The mean denotes the average value of the data set, the minimum denotes the least value in the observation, the maximum denotes the greatest value among the variables in the data set, and the standard deviation denotes the level of dispersion. It has been noted that the return on assets, which was the financial performance, has an average value of 2.37% with a range of -9.53% to 22.65%. This suggests that an average return of 2.37% is anticipated for every naira invested in the assets of the listed banks.

Hypothesis One

There is no significant influence of control environment on return on assets of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria.

Table 4.2 Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.223 ^a	.050	.039	1.90791	1.067

A. Predictors: (Constant), Control Environment

B. Dependent Variable: Financial Performance

Source: *Researcher's Analytic Output (2023)*

Table 4.3 ANOVA for Hypothesis One

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	16.931	1	16.931	4.651	.034 ^b
	Residual	33.970	89	3.640		
	Total	30.901	90			

A. Dependent Variable: Financial Performance

B. Predictors: (Constant), Control Environment

Source: Researcher's Computation (2023)

Table 4.4 Coefficients for Hypothesis One

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	5.408	.327		16.519	.000		
	Control Environment	1.7607	.000	.223	2.157	.034	1.000	1.000

A. Dependent Variable: Financial Performance

Source: Researcher's Analytic Output (2023)

The first hypothesis stated that the financial performance of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria is not considerably impacted by the control environment. The p-value of 0.034 in tables 4.3 and 4.4, which is less than 0.05 and in accordance with the study's decision procedure, allowed for the rejection of the null hypothesis and acceptance of the alternative. Because the computed t-value of 2.157 is higher than the critical value of t, which was 1.986, the null hypothesis was also rejected.

Hypothesis Two

There is no significant influence of risk assessment on return on asset of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria.

Table 4.5 Model Summary for Hypothesis Two

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.354 ^a	.125	.115	27.32200	1.344

A. Predictors: (Constant), Risk Assessment

B. Dependent Variable: ROA

Source: Researcher's Analytic Output (2023)

Table 4.6 ANOVA for Hypothesis Two

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	9507.561	1	9507.561	12.736	.001 ^b
	Residual	66437.736	89	746.491		
	Total	75945.297	90			

A. Dependent Variable: ROA

B. Predictors: (Constant), Risk Assessment

Source: *Researcher's Analytic Output (2023)*

Table 4.7 Coefficients for Hypothesis Two

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	78.362	11.837		6.620	.000		
	RISK ASSESMENT	-5.892	1.651	-.354	-3.569	.001	1.000	1.000

A. Dependent Variable: ROA

Source: *Researcher's Analytic Output (2023)*

The second hypothesis claimed that financial performance of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria is not considerably impacted by risk assessment. Because the p-value of 0.001 given in tables 4.6 and 4.7 is less than 0.05 in accordance with the study's decision rule, the null hypothesis was rejected, and the alternative was accepted. Because the calculated t-value of 3.569 is higher than the critical value of t, which was 1.986, the null hypothesis was also rejected.

Hypothesis three

There is no significant influence of control activities on return on assets of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria.

Table 4.8 Model Summary for Hypothesis Three

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.974 ^a	.948	.947	.44644	1.941

A. Predictors: (Constant), Control Activities

B. Dependent Variable: Financial Performance

Source: *Researcher's Analytic Output (2023)*

Table 4.9 ANOVA for Hypothesis Three

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	323.163	1	323.163	1621.454	.000 ^b
	Residual	17.738	89	.199		
	Total	340.901	90			

A. Dependent Variable: Financial Performance

B. Predictors: (Constant), Control Activities

Source: *Researcher's Analytic Output (2023)*

Table 4.10 Coefficients for Hypothesis Three

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-4.518	.265		-17.077	.000
	CONTROL ACTIVITIES	13.897	.345	.974	40.267	.000

A. Dependent Variable: Financial Performance

Source: *Researcher's Analytic Output (2023)*

According to the third hypothesis, Control Activities in Nigeria's listed deposit money banks do not have a substantial impact on their financial performance. Because the p-value of 0.000 reported in Tables 4.9 and 4.10 is less than 0.05 in accordance with the study's decision rule, the null hypothesis was rejected, and the alternative was accepted. Because the calculated t-value of 40.267 is higher than the critical value of t, which was 1.986, the null hypothesis was also rejected.

Hypothesis Four

There is no significant influence of information and communication on return on assets of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria.

Table 4.11 Model Summary for hypothesis Four

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.197 ^a	.039	.028	1.91886	1.083

A. Predictors: (Constant), Information and Communication

B. Dependent Variable: Financial Performance

Source: *Researcher's Analytic Output (2023)*

Table 4.12 ANOVA for hypothesis Four

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	13.202	1	13.202	3.586	.032 ^b
	Residual	327.699	89	3.682		
	Total	340.901	90			

A. Dependent Variable: Financial Performance

B. Predictors: (Constant), Information and Communication

Source: *Researcher's Analytic Output (2023)*

Table 4.13 Coefficients for Hypothesis Four

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		Beta	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	.329	2.984		.110	.913		
	INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION	.890	.470	.197	2.894	.032	1.000	1.000

A. Dependent Variable: Financial Performance

Source: *Researcher's Analytic Output (2023)*

The fourth hypothesis claimed that the financial performance of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria is considerably impacted by information and communication. Because the p-value of 0.032 reported in Tables 4.12 and 4.13 is less than 0.05 in accordance with the study's decision rule, the null hypothesis was rejected, and the alternative was accepted. Because the calculated t-value of 2.894 is higher than the critical value of t, which was 1.986, the null hypothesis was also rejected.

Hypothesis Five

There is no significant influence of monitoring on return on asset of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria.

Table 4.14 Model Summary for Hypothesis Five

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.152 ^a	.023	.012	28.87020	1.183

A. Predictors: (Constant), Monitoring

B. Dependent Variable: Financial Performance

Source: *Researcher's Analytic Output (2023)*

Table 4.15 ANOVA for Hypothesis Five

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1764.844	1	1764.844	2.117	.149 ^b
	Residual	74180.452	89	833.488		
	Total	75945.297	90			

A. Dependent Variable: Financial Performance

B. Predictors: (Constant), Monitoring

Source: *Researcher's Analytic Output (2023)*

Table 4.16 Coefficients for Hypothesis Five

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	29.333	6.300		4.656	.000		
	MONITORING	10.452	7.183	.152	1.455	.149	1.000	1.000

A. Dependent Variable: Financial Performance

Source: *Researcher's Analytic Output (2023)*

The fifth hypothesis held that Monitoring had no significant influence on the financial success of Nigeria's listed deposit money banks. Because the p-value of 0.149 reported in Tables 4.16 and 4.17 is greater than 0.05 in accordance with the study's decision rule, this null hypothesis was accepted and the alternate rejected. The computed t-value of 1.455 is smaller than the critical value of t, which was 1.986, hence the null hypothesis was also accepted.

4.2. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The analysis shows that the return on assets, which was the financial performance, has an average value of 2.37% and a range from -9.53% to 22.65%. This implies that an average return of 2.37% is anticipated for every naira invested in the assets of the tested banks. The results of the data analysis show an R² value of 0.716, which means that the internal control system of the banks in Nigeria accounts for 71.6% of the variation in the financial performance of the sampled banks. The analysis demonstrated that when all the parts are combined, internal control system has a considerable impact on the bank's financial performance. This finding is in line with that of Uwaoma and Ordu (2015), who discovered that strong internal control improves an organization's ability to manage its finances. Based on the results of the test of hypothesis one, the individual effects of the internal control components on the financial performance of banks were evaluated.

Based on hypothesis one, it was discovered that the control environment strongly influences the financial performance of banks in Nigeria. The regression result shows that the standardized beta coefficient was -0.223, indicating that -22.3% of the profit made by the banks is influenced by the control environment put in place by the

banks. This result contradicts that of Akinleye and Kolawole (2019), who showed that the control environment had a negligible impact on the organizational performance of the chosen tertiary institution.

According to the findings of the test of hypothesis two, risk assessment has a considerable impact on the financial performance of Nigerian banks. According to the regression coefficient, the standardized beta coefficient was -0.354, meaning that the risk assessment systems put in place by the banks have a negative impact on -35.4% of their profit margins. This result is consistent with that of Sawalga and Qtish (2012), who discovered that risk assessment had a considerable impact on financial performance.

Derived from the findings of the test of hypothesis three, control activities have a major impact on financial performance of Nigerian banks. The regression coefficient shows that the standardized beta coefficient was 0.974, indicating that 97.4% of the banks' profits are influenced by the control measures they have in place. This finding concurs with those of Akinleye and Kolawole (2019), who discovered that control activities had a significant impact on the organizational performance of the chosen tertiary institutions. It contrasts Sawalga and Qtish's (2012) finding that control activities do not significantly contribute to the growth of the organization.

Considering the findings of the test of hypothesis four, information and communication have a significant impact on the financial performance of Nigerian banks. The regression result shows that the standardized beta coefficient was 0.197, indicating that 19.7% of the profit made by the banks is influenced by the information and communication efforts implemented by the banks. This result is consistent with Kumuthiridevi's (2016) conclusion that information and communication activities in Private Banks of Trincomalee moderately support the efficacy of internal control systems.

According to the findings of the fifth hypothesis test, monitoring has a negligible impact on the financial performance of Nigerian banks. According to the regression coefficient, the standardized beta coefficient was 0.152, meaning that the banks' monitoring programs have an impact on 15.2% of their revenue. The monitoring activities component of the internal control systems of banks in Ghana was highly regarded by the respondents with an average mean of 4.46, which is in contrast to the finding of Ayagre, Gyamerah, and Nartey (2014), who found that strong control exists in those components.

The aforesaid data imply that a key factor in financial success is the activities of the banks' internal control systems and the control environment they have established. The results also highlight the important relationship between financial performance and internal control system. The results also show that the banks' control environment, risk assessment, and control actions are highly influenced by financial performance. This result backs up a number of bank collapse claims about the management and director of the bank's control operations, control environment, and risk assessment.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the study's findings, it is concluded that the Control environment significantly influences the financial performance of banks in Nigeria, as do risk assessment, control activities vis-a-vis information and communication. While monitoring activities have a negligible impact on financial performance of deposit money banks. Therefore, maximizing return on assets of deposit money banks in Nigeria requires having proper internal control components. Additionally, the researcher suggests the following;

- i. Controlling measures should be meted on deposited funds because the banking industry is risky and has an impact on the nation's economic growth while banks should maintain a solid control environment approach to internal control.
- ii. In order to continue evaluating the riskiness of their operations, management should make sure that banks have an independent board of directors and audit committee as a prerequisite of corporate governance regulatory standards.
- iii. Management should ensure that banks have joint control so that activities there are given the attention they need.
- iv. Management should make sure that banks have an information and communication system in place that makes it easy to communicate timely, relevant, and trustworthy information to stakeholders, in order to speed up the flow of information between management and staff.
- v. Management should keep an eye on and oversee Nigeria's deposit money banks to ensure that financial reporting, legal and regulatory requirements are met, and that regular, transparent reporting to stakeholders on corporate governance, risk management, and internal control is enhanced.

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